

Homogeneous nucleation rate of carbon dioxide hydrate formation under experimental condition from Seeding simulations

I. M. Zerón,¹ J. Algaba,¹ J. M. Míguez,¹ J. Grabowska,² S. Blazquez,³ E. Sanz,³ C. Vega,³ and F. J. Blas^{*1}

¹Laboratorio de Simulación Molecular y Química Computacional, CIQSO-Centro de Investigación en Química Sostenible and Departamento de Ciencias Integradas, Universidad de Huelva, 21006 Huelva Spain

²Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, Gdansk University of Technology, ul. Narutowicza 11/12, 80-233 Gdansk, Poland

³Dpto. Química Física I, Fac. Ciencias Químicas, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, 28040 Madrid, Spain

We investigate the nucleation of carbon dioxide (CO₂) hydrates from carbon dioxide aqueous solutions by means of molecular dynamics simulations using the TIP4P/Ice and the TraPPE models for water and CO₂ respectively. We work at 400 bar and different temperatures and CO₂ concentrations. We use brute force molecular dynamics when the supersaturation or the supercooling are so high so that nucleation occurs spontaneously and Seeding otherwise. We used both methods for a particular state and found an excellent agreement when using a linear combination of \bar{q}_3 and \bar{q}_{12} order parameters to identify critical clusters. With such order parameter we get a rate of $10^{25} \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for nucleation in a CO₂ saturated solution at 255 K (35 K supercooling). By comparison with our previous work on methane hydrates, we conclude that nucleation of CO₂ hydrates is several orders of magnitude faster due to a lower interfacial free energy between the crystal and the solution. By combining our nucleation studies with a recent calculation of the hydrate-solution interfacial free energy at coexistence [Algaba *et al.*, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **623**, 354–367 (2022)], we obtain a prediction of the nucleation rate temperature dependence for CO₂-saturated solutions (the experimentally relevant concentration). On the one hand, we open the window for comparison with experiments for supercooling larger than 25 K. On the other hand, we conclude that homogeneous nucleation is impossible for supercooling lower than 20 K. Therefore, nucleation must be heterogeneous in typical experiments where hydrate formation is observed at low supercooling. To assess the hypothesis that nucleation occurs at the solution-CO₂ interface we run spontaneous nucleation simulations in two-phase systems and find, by comparison with single-phase simulations, that the interface does not affect hydrate nucleation, at least at the deep supercooling at which this study was carried out (40 and 45 K). Overall, our work sheds light on molecular and thermodynamic aspects of hydrate nucleation.

*Corresponding author: felipe@uhu.es

I. INTRODUCTION

When a liquid is cooled below the solid-liquid coexistence temperature, the crystallization is not an immediate process and the liquid can remain in a metastable supercooled state for some time. Fluctuations still exist and the formation of small embryos of the stable crystal phase can be observed. When these fluctuations lead to the formation of a solid cluster that surpasses a critical size then crystallization cannot be avoided. This mechanism is usually known as homogeneous nucleation. In the proximity of the equilibrium freezing temperature, the critical cluster size is quite large and the liquid phase can remain stable for quite a long time. The presence of solid impurities reduces the size of the critical cluster and makes nucleation easier, leading to heterogeneous nucleation that can be observed easily even for temperatures moderately below the freezing temperature.¹

An interesting observable is the nucleation rate J defined as the number of critical clusters per unit of time and volume. The nucleation rate can be determined in experiments, mainly for ice in supercooled water^{2–11} but only (due to limitations in system size and accessible time) when its value is smaller than $10^{16}/(\text{m}^3 \text{ s})$. In simulations, the nucleation rate can be determined in brute force (BF) simulations only when its value is of the order of $10^{30}/(\text{m}^3 \text{ s})$ or higher (due to limitations in

system size and accessible time). Thus, there is a range of nucleation rates between $10^{16} - 10^{30}/(\text{m}^3 \text{ s})$ that cannot be accessed either by experiments or by BF simulations. However, using special rare event technique simulations allows to determine the nucleation rate in this intermediate regime or even for temperatures accessible in experiments.

Several techniques have been proposed to obtain nucleation rates in simulations when BF simulations are not sufficient. Two of them: Umbrella Sampling¹² (US) and Metadynamics¹³ are aimed at determining the free energy barrier for nucleation and the nucleation rate using the formalism proposed by Volmer and Weber¹⁴ and Becker and Döring.¹⁵ About 25 years ago Bolhuis and coworkers proposed a methodology, the Transition Path Sampling (TPS),¹⁶ where an analysis of the trajectories that are reactive (i.e., leading from the metastable phase to the stable phase) is performed, allowing the determination of nucleation rates. About twenty years ago another method, the Forward Flux Sampling (FFS),¹⁷ was proposed to analyze the fraction of successful trajectories leading from one value of the order parameter to the next and the flux to the initial lowest order value of the order parameter considered. The nucleation rates obtained by these four methods (Umbrella Sampling, Metadynamics, Transition Path Sampling, and Forward Flux Sampling) are in principle exact (or almost exact) for the considered potential model.

More recently some of us¹⁸ and independently Knott *et al.*¹⁹ introduced a new approximate technique to determine

nucleation rates known as Seeding. In this technique, a solid cluster is inserted into a metastable fluid and the conditions at which this cluster is critical (i.e., with 50% probability of evolving to either phase) are determined. This followed the first ideas about using seeds for nucleation studies introduced by Bai and Li.^{20,21} Once the size of the critical cluster is determined then the expression of the Classical Nucleation Theory (CNT) is used to estimate the nucleation rate. The main disadvantage of Seeding is that it is an approximate technique as the results depend on the choice of the order parameter. However, its main advantage is its simplicity thus, allowing to study really complex systems for which more rigorous methods are too expensive from a computational point of view. It has been shown that with appropriate order parameters, Seeding correctly predicts the nucleation rates of hard spheres, Lennard-Jones systems,²² electrolytes²³ or even the nucleation of ice both from pure water and from aqueous electrolyte solutions.^{24,25} Recently we have shown that it can also predict the nucleation rate of hydrate formation for the methane hydrate.²⁶

Hydrates are non-stoichiometric solids formed when a gas (typically methane or carbon dioxide) is in contact with water under moderate pressure (i.e., 30 – 1000 bar) and the system is cooled. In the most common hydrate structure (sI) the unit cell has cubic symmetry and contains 46 molecules of water and 8 molecules of guest (occupying two types of cavities, six large and two somewhat smaller).^{27–29} Methane hydrates can be found naturally on the seafloor near the coasts and it is also formed in the pipes transporting natural gas.³⁰ It is also expected to be found on some planets.³¹ Although the methane hydrate is the most relevant, the interest in the hydrate containing carbon dioxide (CO₂) is growing. This is so because replacing methane by CO₂ in the hydrate would be a simple procedure to sequester CO₂ from the atmosphere and to mitigate its greenhouse effect that leads to global warming.^{32,33}

When the gas is in contact with water the formation of the hydrate starts at a certain temperature denoted as T_3 .²⁷ This temperature is indeed a triple point, where three phases: the solid hydrate, the aqueous solution, and the gas, coexist at equilibrium. The value of T_3 depends on the pressure, and nucleation rates increase dramatically as one moves from T_3 to lower temperatures at constant pressure.

Several experimental studies deal with hydrate nucleation.^{34–41} Many computational studies on hydrate nucleation have also been reported.^{19,29,42?–65} Comparison between experimental and simulation studies is difficult due to the presence of heterogeneous nucleation in experiments, and to the fact that in many simulation studies one must use large supersaturations (i.e., solubilities of the gas artificially higher than the experimental ones) to increase the driving force to facilitate the kinetics of the nucleation process. In their pioneering molecular dynamics study, Walsh *et al.*⁴⁶ used a high concentration of methane in the aqueous solution in order to observe nucleation events in a reasonable simulation time. In fact, using a supersaturated solution of the guest molecule is a common strategy in the studies of nucleation of hydrates. There are two ways to prepare such a system. The first one is to use a homogeneous solution of guest molecule in water,^{49,50}

in which the concentration of solute is higher than the equilibrium solubility under the same conditions. However, this is only possible at low temperatures, where the nucleation of hydrate is faster than the nucleation of gas bubbles.⁶⁶ The second option is to use a system in which there is a curved interface between the solution and a gas phase^{46,55–57} (i.e., bubbles of gas in the solution). The presence of a curved interface results in an increase in the solubility of the guest molecule in water. These two methods allow to obtain spontaneous nucleation events in BF simulations.^{46,49,50} Additionally, Arjun *et al.*^{55–57} were able to estimate the nucleation rate of hydrates at temperatures well below the T_3 by combining transition path sampling with the use of gas bubbles, that increases the solubility of the gas. In experiments, however, the concentration of guest molecules in the solution is dictated by the equilibrium solubility of the solute in water *via* a planar interface. For that reason, in this work we study the nucleation of hydrate under experimental conditions, i.e., we use the concentration of guest molecule (CO₂ in this work) equal to its equilibrium solubility. To the best of our knowledge, there are only two simulation studies where the nucleation rate was computed under "realistic experimental conditions" (without supersaturation) for the formation of the methane hydrate. In the first one, Arjun and Bolhuis⁵⁸ in a tour of force used TPS to determine the nucleation rate. In the second one, we used the Seeding technique.²⁶ Good agreement was found between the estimates of the nucleation rate from these two studies.

In this work, we shall use the *Seeding* technique²² to determine by computer simulations the homogeneous nucleation rate of the CO₂ hydrate at the pressure of 400 bar and when the supercooling $\Delta T = T_3 - T$, (i.e., the difference between the dissociation temperature T_3 at the current temperature T) is equal to 35 K. We shall determine the nucleation rate under experimental conditions (i.e., without supersaturation). This study is a follow-up of a previous study where we used the same technique to study the nucleation rate of methane hydrate at the same pressure and degree of supercooling²⁶. The comparison will be useful as it illustrates the differences in the nucleation rate of hydrates of methane and CO₂ at the same thermodynamic conditions (i.e., equal pressure and degree of supercooling). At first, one would expect that the differences between both gases should not be too large as the guest molecules are of similar size. However, the solubility of CO₂ in water is an order of magnitude larger than that of methane (due to its large quadrupole moment leading to more favorable water-gas interactions). It will be shown that the nucleation rate of CO₂ hydrate is much higher for a certain fixed pressure and a certain fixed supercooling compared to methane hydrate. The comparison is especially useful as we are using the same water model that was employed in our previous study of methane, namely TIP4P/Ice. This higher nucleation rate for the CO₂ hydrate is due to the lower value of the interfacial free energy between the hydrate and the aqueous solution rather than to its higher solubility.

Finally, we shall analyze the impact of the gas-water interface on the nucleation rate. Hydrates are always obtained in experiments by considering a two-phase system (gas in contact with water). There is the possibility that the presence

of the interface facilitates the nucleation of the solid phase. Thus, heterogeneous nucleation (due to the presence of the gas-water interface rather than to the presence of solid impurities in the liquid phase) may be responsible for the nucleation found in experiments. To determine this point we performed simulations both in the presence and in the absence of the interface with the same concentration of CO₂ in aqueous solution. We conclude that nucleation rates obtained in both cases were the same, suggesting that the gas-water interface does not enhance the nucleation rate, at least for the thermodynamic conditions considered in this work.

The organization of this paper is as follows. In Sec. II, we describe the methodology used in this work. The results obtained, as well as their discussion, are described in Sec. III. Finally, conclusions are presented in Sec. IV.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Seeding: A brief description

From the description of the CNT,^{14,15,67,68} the formation of a solid cluster of size N at given temperature T and pressure P into the liquid phase requires a free energy of formation ΔG given by:

$$\Delta G = -N|\Delta\mu_N| + \gamma\mathcal{A} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\mu_N$ is the driving force for nucleation. In the case of a pure substance, it is just the difference in chemical potentials of the solid and fluid phases at the considered thermodynamic conditions. In the case of hydrate formation is just the difference between the chemical potential of the solid phase and that of the molecules of the hydrate in the fluid phase (we shall come to this point later). γ is the solid-liquid interfacial free energy, and \mathcal{A} is the interfacial area. Since the first term is negative and grows with N and the second is positive and grows with the area (i.e., $N^{2/3}$) a maximum is reached for a certain value of N (i.e., the size of the critical cluster N_c) leading to a free energy barrier of ΔG_c :

$$\Delta G_c = \frac{1}{2}N_c|\Delta\mu_N| \quad (2)$$

The size of the critical cluster can be obtained as:

$$N_c = \frac{32\pi\gamma^3}{3\rho_s^2|\Delta\mu_N|^3} \quad (3)$$

where ρ_s is the number density of the bulk solid phase at the considered P and T of the system (in CNT one neglects changes in the density of the solid in the critical cluster due to the Laplace pressure which is equivalent to assume that the solid phase is incompressible). The free energy barrier can also be rewritten as

$$\Delta G_c = \frac{16\pi\gamma^3}{3\rho_s^2|\Delta\mu_N|^2} \quad (4)$$

According to CNT, if a steady state is considered, i.e., the distribution of clusters of different sizes does not depend on time, the nucleation rate per unit volume J at a given temperature T is the product of the probability of a critical nucleus formation, which depends on the free energy of formation ΔG_c as $\mathcal{P}(N_c) \approx e^{-\Delta G_c/k_B T}$ and a kinetic factor J_0 :

$$J = J_0 e^{-\Delta G_c/k_B T} = \rho_f Z f^+ e^{-\Delta G_c/k_B T} \quad (5)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and the $J_0 = \rho_f Z f^+$ term contains the kinetic growth information through the fluid number density ρ_f . Z is the the Zeldovich factor which is given by:

$$Z = \sqrt{\frac{|\Delta G_c''|}{2\pi k_B T}} = \sqrt{\frac{|\Delta\mu_N|}{6\pi k_B T N_c}} \quad (6)$$

Here $\Delta G_c''$ is the curvature of the free energy formation at the critical size.

The attachment rate f^+ which can be calculated via an effective diffusion constant that accounts for the number of particles aggregated and separated in time from the critical cluster as follows:

$$f^+ = \frac{\langle \Delta N_c^2(t) \rangle}{2t} = \frac{\langle [N_c(t) - N_c(t_0)]^2 \rangle}{2t} \quad (7)$$

We have shown in previous work²⁶ that the corresponding expression of CNT for the hydrate nucleation can be written as:

$$J = \rho_L^{\text{CO}_2} Z f_{\text{CO}_2}^+ \exp\left(\frac{-N_c^{\text{CO}_2} |\Delta\mu_N|}{2k_B T}\right) \quad (8)$$

where $\rho_L^{\text{CO}_2}$ is the number density of CO₂ in the liquid phase, $N_c^{\text{CO}_2}$ is the number of molecules of CO₂ in the critical cluster (notice that the critical cluster contains both molecules of water and molecules of CO₂) and $f_{\text{CO}_2}^+$ is the attachment rate computed from Eq. (7) by analyzing the diffusive behavior or the number of CO₂ molecules in the solid cluster when starting from configurations at the critical size. The value of γ can be obtained from Eq.(3) by using $\rho_s^{\text{CO}_2}$ which is just the number density of molecules of CO₂ in the hydrate.

In the Seeding technique, a solid cluster is inserted into the metastable fluid and the thermodynamic conditions at which is critical (i.e., 50% of probability of either melting or growing is determined). Once the size of the critical cluster N_c is known one determines the free energy barrier using Eq. (2). The value of $\rho_L^{\text{CO}_2}$ is determined from the solubility of CO₂ at the considered value of P and T (or with a higher value in the case of supersaturated solutions as it will be shown later on). The only remaining ingredient is $\Delta\mu_N$ which will be described in detail in the next subsection.

B. Driving Force for nucleation

$\Delta\mu_N$ can be viewed, as first suggested by Kashchiev and Firoozabadi⁶⁹ (see also our previous works^{26,66,70}), as a chemical reaction that takes place at constant P and T . In fact $\Delta\mu_N$ is just the chemical potential change of the following physical process:

In Eq. (9), one molecule of CO_2 in the aqueous solution reacts with 5.75 molecules of water (also in the aqueous solution phase) to form a $[\text{CO}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{5.75}]_{\text{H}}$ “hydrate molecule” in the solid phase. Since we are assuming, as in our previous works,^{26,66,70} that all cages of the hydrates are filled. A unit cell of CO_2 hydrate is formed by 46 water molecules and 8 CO_2 molecules, i.e., one molecule of CO_2 reacts with $46/8 = 5.75$ water molecules. This is consistent with the stoichiometric reaction given by Eq. (9).

Since all cages of the hydrate are occupied, the chemical potential of this compound (hydrate) can be obtained as the sum of the chemical potential of CO_2 in the solid plus 5.75 times the chemical potential of water in the solid (see Eq. (8) of our previous paper⁷⁰). Note that the chemical potentials depend on T and P (and on composition). However, all the results of this work were obtained for a pressure of 400 bar. For this reason, we shall omit the pressure dependence and will write the chemical potential of the hydrate simply as $\mu_{\text{H}}^{\text{H}}(T)$ (there is no dependence on composition for the hydrate as its stoichiometry is fixed). Following the work of Kashchiev and Firoozabadi⁶⁹ and our previous works,^{26,66,70} the driving force for nucleation of the hydrate formed from the aqueous solution with a concentration x_{CO_2} at T can be expressed as:

$$\Delta\mu_N(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}) = \mu_{\text{H}}^{\text{H}}(T) - \mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}) - 5.75 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2}) \quad (10)$$

where $\mu_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2})$ is the chemical potential of CO_2 in the aqueous solution, and $\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{aq}}(T, x_{\text{CO}_2})$ is the chemical potential of water in the aqueous solution.

The nucleation rate of the CO_2 hydrate has been determined by using BF simulations for most of the cases. In BF runs J is determined directly and it is not necessary to know the value of $\Delta\mu_N$. However, for two thermodynamic states, it was necessary to use the Seeding method, and therefore it was necessary to obtain the value of $\Delta\mu_N$ to determine the nucleation rate. In this context, it is useful to introduce the supersaturation at a given pressure P and temperature T defined as:

$$S = \frac{x_{\text{CO}_2}}{x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}} \quad (11)$$

where x_{CO_2} is the CO_2 molar fraction of a solution and $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}$ is the CO_2 molar fraction at experimental conditions, i.e., the CO_2 concentration in water when in equilibrium with pure CO_2 via a planar interface at the same P and T . In particular, we used the Seeding method for $T = 255 \text{ K}$ when $S = 1$

and when $S = 1.207$. Note that this is the setup used in experimental work. We shall also determine J from Seeding at 255 K for the case $S = 1.207$. This case is interesting as for this particular state it is possible to determine J both from BF runs and from the Seeding method and this state serves as a cross-check of the Seeding method (in particular of the choice of the order parameter). The states for which we determined J in this work are shown in Fig. 1 as diamonds and triangles.

Since Seeding is used here only for two thermodynamic states at 255 K and 400 bar, namely $S = 1$ and $S = 1.207$ only the values of $\Delta\mu_N$ for these two states are needed. In our previous work,⁷⁰ the driving force for nucleation of the hydrate of CO_2 has been obtained using four independent methods along the solubility curve obtained when a CO_2 -rich phase is in contact with an aqueous phase at 400 bar and several temperatures below the dissociation temperature. Particularly, we have proposed a novel methodology to evaluate the driving force for nucleation based on the calculation of partial enthalpies of CO_2 and water in the aqueous phase at different values of CO_2 composition and temperatures (we recommend to read Section E.4 of our previous work⁷⁰ for further details). This is a rigorous methodology obtained only from thermodynamic arguments for calculating the driving force for nucleation of the CO_2 hydrate at any P , T and x_{CO_2} . According to this, it is possible to directly determine the value of the driving force for nucleation at 255 K and 400 bar, at the equilibrium solubility composition (i.e., $S = 1$ or $x_{\text{CO}_2} = x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}} = 0.0803$) when a CO_2 -rich phase is in contact with an aqueous phase via a planar interface, being it of -2.26 (in $k_B T$ units) at $S = 1$ and -2.73 (in $k_B T$ units) for the case $S = 1.207$. See the work of Algaba *et al.*⁷⁰ for further details, and more specifically the route 4 for calculating the driving force (Eq. (26) in that paper) and Fig. 14 (also there) from which these values are extrapolated.

C. Simulation details

All Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations are performed using the GROMACS package.^{71,72} We use the Verlet leapfrog algorithm⁷³ with a time step of 2 fs. The temperature is kept constant using the Nosé-Hoover thermostat with a relaxation time of 2 ps.^{74,75} The pressure is also kept constant but using the Parrinello-Rahman barostat⁷⁶ with the same relaxation time. We use two different versions of the NPT or isothermal-isobaric ensemble. For BF simulations and Seeding simulations at supersaturated conditions, we use the isotropic NPT , i.e., the three sides of the simulation box are changed proportionally to keep the pressure constant. For Seeding simulations at experimental conditions, i.e., at coexistence conditions at which the aqueous solution of CO_2 and the CO_2 -rich liquid phase coexist, we use the anisotropic $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ ensemble since a planar liquid-liquid interface exists and only fluctuations of the volume are performed varying the length of the simulation box along the z -axis direction, perpendicular to the planar interface. We use a cutoff distance of 1 nm for dispersive and Coulombic interactions. For electrostatic interactions, we use the Particle Mesh Ewald (PME) method.⁷⁷ We do not use long-range corrections for dispersive interactions.

Water and CO₂ molecules are described using the TIP4P/Ice⁷⁸ and TraPPE⁷⁹ models, respectively. TIP4P/Ice predicts correctly the melting point of ice Ih and that guarantees good predictions for the phase equilibria of hydrates.⁸⁰ The water-CO₂ unlike dispersive interactions are taken into account via the modified Berthelot rule proposed by Míguez *et al.*⁸¹ and also used in our previous work.⁷⁰ This strategy allows us to predict accurately the three-phase CO₂ hydrate-water-CO₂ coexistence or dissociation line of the CO₂ hydrate. Particularly, with this choice the dissociation temperature or T_3 , at 400 bar, is in excellent agreement with experimental data taken from the literature (see Fig. 10 and Table II of the work of Míguez *et al.*⁸¹ for further details). It is also important to mention that the same molecular parameters can accurately predict the CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial free energy.^{82–84}

The dissociation temperature or T_3 of the CO₂ hydrate at 400 bar is 290 K⁷⁰ (close to the experimental value at this pressure which is 286 K). In this work, all simulations are carried out at 245, 250, and 255 K (supercoolings of 45, 40, and 35 K, respectively). Following our previous work,²⁶ we perform three different kinds of simulations to determine the nucleation rate of the CO₂ hydrate at 255 K: (1) BF simulations at supersaturation conditions; (2) Seeding simulations at supersaturation conditions; and (3) Seeding simulations at experimental saturated conditions. In the first set of simulations, we estimate the nucleation rate of the hydrate at two different saturated conditions using its definition and the mean first-passage time approach (MFPT). In the second set, we also determine the nucleation rate at one of the supersaturation conditions following the Seeding approach. This allows us to check if the local bond order parameters used to characterize the size of the critical cluster of the hydrate are appropriate. Finally, in the third set of simulations and once we have got the best selection of the order parameters, we estimate the nucleation rate of the CO₂ hydrate at experimental conditions, i.e., at the equilibrium (saturated) conditions of CO₂ in water in contact with a CO₂-rich liquid phase via a planar interface using the Seeding Technique.

We perform BF simulations in the isotropic NPT ensemble at 255 K placing 4942 water molecules and 530 and 560 CO₂ molecules, respectively (i.e., $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0969$ and $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.1018$) in a cubic simulation box as shown in Fig. 2a. As the concentration of CO₂ in water at coexistence conditions is $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}} = 0.0803$,⁷⁰ the systems considered correspond to $S = 1.207$ and $S = 1.268$ respectively. In all cases, the system is equilibrated during 5 – 10 ns and run during up to 3 μ s. This simulation time allows us to observe the formation of solid clusters of the CO₂ hydrate. We show in Fig. 1 some of the states for which we determined the nucleation rate at 255 K. The states simulated using BF simulations at this temperature are represented as black triangles. In our previous works, we have determined the dissociation temperature T_3 of the CO₂ and CH₄ hydrates using the so-called solubility method and calculating the crossing point (maroon circle) between the solubility curves of CO₂ in the aqueous solution when it is in contact with the CO₂ liquid phase and the hydrate, as it is shown in Fig. 1. This methodology has also been used in previous work by Tanaka and coworkers (see Fig. 9 of

FIG. 1. CO₂ molar fraction, x_{CO_2} , in an aqueous solution coexisting with the hydrate (blue curve) and with a CO₂ fluid reservoir (red curve), as functions of temperature, at 400 bar. Diamonds and triangles represent the six states at which the nucleation rate of CO₂ hydrate, J , is obtained in this work using BF simulations (diamonds) and the Seeding technique (triangles). Red color symbols are used to denote saturated conditions ($S = 1$) and black color symbols to denote supersaturated conditions ($S > 1$). Note that at 255 K and $S = 1.207$ we have estimated J from BF and Seeding simulations. The crossing point between both curves (maroon circle) corresponds to the temperature T_3 at which hydrate, solution, and CO₂ coexist.^{66,85} The green square represents the hydrate–solution coexistence point at 255 K.

their work).⁸⁵

We also perform Seeding simulations at one of the two supersaturated concentrations, $S = 1.207$. According to the Seeding technique, a spherical cluster of CO₂ hydrate is inserted into a supersaturated aqueous phase of CO₂ in water, as it is shown in Fig. 2b. To do this, we first consider two bulk phases, one of CO₂ hydrate and another of an aqueous solution of CO₂ with the appropriate supersaturation ($S = 1.207$), at 255 K and 400 bar. The aqueous solution of CO₂ is identical to that used in the BF simulations (4942 water molecules and 530 CO₂ molecules). The hydrate simulation box is formed from 2944 molecules of water and 512 CO₂ molecules. This corresponds to a $4 \times 4 \times 4$ unit cell of sI hydrate structure with full occupancy. The space group of the unit cell is $Pm\bar{3}n$. The proton disorder was obtained using the algorithm of Buch *et al.*⁸⁶ Both simulation boxes are equilibrated in the NPT ensemble separately. The hydrate system is equilibrated during 50 ns. After this time, a spherical cluster of radius ranging from 1 to 1.4 nm is cut and immersed into the saturated aqueous solution of CO₂ in water. This is practically done by removing water and CO₂ molecules and creating a spherical empty space with the same radius of seed of the spherical hydrate cluster. Overlaps in the interface are avoided by slightly moving or rotating nearby molecules. We recommend the reader our previous work for further details.⁶⁶

Additionally, we run Seeding simulations at coexistence conditions, i.e., the aqueous solution of CO₂ at which the hydrate cluster is inserted into a solution in equilibrium with a CO₂-rich liquid phase via a planar interface at 255 K and

400 bar. This corresponds to a molar fraction of CO_2 in water $x_{\text{CO}_2} = x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}} = 0.0803$. This state corresponds to the black diamond represented in Fig. 1 at 255 K. Note that there is a black triangle in that state since we have also run BF simulations at the same thermodynamic conditions.

To keep this concentration constant, the hydrate seed is inserted into the aqueous solution in contact with a CO_2 -rich liquid phase, as shown in Fig. 2c. In this case, since there is a planar interface in the simulation box, we perform the simulations in the $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ anisotropic ensemble. The aqueous solution - CO_2 system is formed from 12000 water molecules and 4952 CO_2 molecules. These are the total number of molecules of the whole system, the aqueous solution of CO_2 and the CO_2 liquid reservoir. Once the system is properly equilibrated, the spherical hydrate is inserted in the center of the aqueous phase in the same way as in the Seeding simulations at supersaturated conditions.

Finally, we also perform additional BF simulations at 245 and 250 K (at 400 bar in both cases). In both cases, however, simulations are performed at $S = 1.0$. i.e., at the corresponding CO_2 saturation concentration. These two states correspond to the red diamonds represented in Fig. 1 at 245 and 250 K. We use two types of simulation setups for this study: a homogeneous CO_2 saturated bulk solution and a saturated solution in contact via a planar interface with a fluid CO_2 reservoir. In the first case, we use isotropic NPT runs. In the second one, we use $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ runs. The reason to determine J in these two different setups is that we want to investigate if the presence of an interface between CO_2 and water enhances/hinders or has no effect on the nucleation rate. At 245 K, we use 2400 and 240 water and CO_2 molecules in the homogeneous system (cubic simulation box with a volume of 82.5 nm^3) and 2400 and 1148 water and CO_2 molecules in the inhomogeneous system (volume of the simulation box equal to 4141.9 nm^3). This corresponds in both cases to a molar fraction of CO_2 in water $x_{\text{CO}_2} = x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}} = 0.09$. At 250 K, we use 6524 and 606 water and CO_2 molecules in the homogeneous system and 7200 and 3444 water and CO_2 molecules in the inhomogeneous system. As in the previous case, in the homogenous system we use a cubic simulation box with a volume of 222.5 nm^3 . In the inhomogeneous system, the volume of the simulation box is 420.1 nm^3 . In this case, the molar fraction of CO_2 in water $x_{\text{CO}_2} = x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}} = 0.085$.

III. RESULTS

A. Order parameter

In general, the size of the largest solid cluster is an adequate order parameter in nucleation studies. To identify the size of the largest solid cluster it is necessary to identify solid and fluid molecules first. A good order parameter should label most of the molecules as fluid when they are in the bulk fluid phase or as solid when they are in the bulk solid phase. The mislabeling (i.e., molecules labeled as solid in the bulk fluid and as liquid in the bulk solid) should be as small as possible and equal in both phases²². To identify water solid particles

FIG. 2. Starting configurations for runs performed in this work to estimate nucleation rates at 400 bar and different temperatures and concentrations. Water and CO_2 molecules are represented as blue and yellow sticks, respectively. Black molecules depict the spherical seed of CO_2 hydrate introduced into the system to induce crystallization. (a) One-phase system of a supersaturated aqueous solution of CO_2 . (b) Two-phase system with a solid cluster of CO_2 hydrate (seed) inserted in the aqueous solution of CO_2 at saturation S . (c) Three-phase system with a CO_2 liquid phase in contact with an aqueous solution of CO_2 via a planar interface and a spherical cluster of CO_2 hydrate inserted in the aqueous solution of CO_2 . In this case, the concentration of CO_2 in water is that of equilibrium ($S = 1$).

we use the averaged order parameters proposed by Lechner and Dellago.⁸⁷ In previous works we have shown that \bar{q}_{12} does a very good job in identifying water molecules in the solid CH_4 hydrate²⁶ but also in other hydrates.⁸⁸ Here we shall use a combination of \bar{q}_3 and \bar{q}_{12} since it provides even better results. Oxygen atoms (and not hydrogen ones) were used when computing the order parameter. To obtain either \bar{q}_3 or \bar{q}_{12} of each water molecule we considered all the water molecules at a distance of 5.5 \AA or less from the molecule of interest (this distance corresponds to the second minimum of the radial distribution function).

We carried out simulations in bulk phases: CO_2 hydrate and aqueous solution of CO_2 at 255 K and 400 bar. The \bar{q}_3 and \bar{q}_{12} values obtained after 50 ns of production are plotted in Fig. 3. As can be seen, this pair of parameters allows to differentiate clearly between the cloud of water molecules in the hydrate phase and that of water in the dissolution. From values plotted in Fig. 3 we determine a threshold function which is a linear combination of \bar{q}_3 and \bar{q}_{12} parameters being $\bar{q}_c = -0.6718\bar{q}_3 + 0.1484$ the best separation causing a mislabeling of just 0.018%. Thus this order parameter is exception-

FIG. 3. Averaged local bond order parameters \bar{q}_3 and \bar{q}_{12} of water molecules for bulk systems at 255K and 400bar. Black pluses correspond to water molecules in the aqueous solution of CO_2 phase at equilibrium concentration $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}}$, red crosses represent water molecules in the hydrate phase, and the threshold with minimum mislabeling²² between two phases is indicated by the blue line $\bar{q}_c = -0.6718\bar{q}_3 + 0.1484$.

ally good at identifying solid and fluid particles. Finally, to determine the number of water molecules in a solid cluster we consider two molecules connected if they are labeled as solid and their separation is less than 3.5 Å. The number of CO_2 is inferred by the hydrate stoichiometry 1 CO_2 : 5.75 H_2O .

It is simple to locate the transition to the solid phase using BF simulations if one has an order parameter that distinguishes reasonably well fluid and solid particles. Estimated nucleation rates do not depend on the choice of the order parameter. However, in the case of Seeding things are different. The estimate of J will depend on the choice of the order parameter. Ideally one should use an order parameter that allows to estimate correctly the radius at the surface of tension of the solid cluster (see previous work for a deeper discussion of this point). In our previous work,²⁶ we have demonstrated that the \bar{q}_{12} local bond order parameters of Lechner and Dellago⁸⁷ is a good choice to get accurate estimates for the nucleation rates of the methane hydrate. Some of us have recently shown that the same is true when the $\bar{q}_3 - \bar{q}_{12}$ combination is used for the methane hydrate, as well as for other hydrates, including nitrogen, hydrogen, and tetrahydrofuran hydrates.⁸⁸ It is necessary to show now that the $\bar{q}_3 - \bar{q}_{12}$ combination is also providing good estimates of J for the CO_2 hydrate within the Seeding formalism. The way to test that is to compare values obtained of J from BF simulations to those obtained from Seeding.

B. Nucleation rate by BF simulations at 255 K and supersaturations $S = 1.207$ and $S = 1.268$

At 255 K and 400 bar we were unable to nucleate hydrates in the two phases system (CO_2 and water) within our computational resources (several thousand molecules and up to 10 microseconds simulations are needed). For this reason, we

decided to consider two supersaturated solutions at 255 K and 400 bar, one with $S = 1.207$, that corresponds to a molar fraction of $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0969$, and another with $S = 1.268$ which corresponds to $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.1016$. Note that although both molar fractions are close to the equilibrium concentration of CO_2 in water at coexistence conditions, $x_{\text{CO}_2}^{\text{eq}} = 0.0803$,⁷⁰ the time required to observe nucleation in BF simulations is very different (see below). The typical volume of the simulation box was 172.4 nm^3 ($S = 1.207$) and 173.4 nm^3 ($S = 1.268$) (containing 4942 molecules of water and 530 or 560 molecules of CO_2 respectively). Runs were done in the isotropic NPT ensemble.

Fig. 4 shows the number of water molecules in the largest cluster of the CO_2 hydrate, n_h , as a function of time for systems with supersaturations $S = 1.207$ and 1.268. In the first case ($S = 1.207$), shown in panel (a), we have considered 15 independent trajectories, and in the second case ($S = 1.268$) shown in panel (b), we have simulated 20 trajectories. For each run, we determine the nucleation time as the one required to cross the horizontal line defined by $n_h > 125$ as this corresponds to a post-critical cluster that never returns to the fluid phase and grows irreversibly. For $S = 1.268$, the twenty trajectories are successful in nucleating the solid phase in less than 1 μs . For $S = 1.207$, 12 out of 15 were successful after runs of up to 3 μs . Let us now compute the nucleation rate. For the case $S = 1.268$ the nucleation rate can be estimated simply as:

$$J_{\text{BF}} = \frac{1}{\tau V}, \quad (12)$$

where τ is the average time required for the system to nucleate. For $S = 1.268$ it is easy to determine this time obtaining a value of about $2 \times 10^{31} / (\text{m}^3 \text{s})$. For $S = 1.207$, not all trajectories are successful in nucleating the solid. In this case, τ could be computed from the time required to nucleate n trajectories out of n_0 by using the expression:

$$\tau = \frac{\tau_{(n_0-n)/n_0}}{\ln\left(\frac{n_0}{n_0-n}\right)} \quad (13)$$

Since we have performed 15 different trajectories, $n = 12$ and $n_0 = 15$, and consequently $\tau_{3/15} = 2240 \text{ ns}$. Using this result, the volume of the simulation box, $V = 172.4 \text{ nm}^3$, and combining Eqs. (12) and (13), the nucleation rate of the CO_2 hydrate in the supersaturated solution with $S = 1.207$ is $J_{\text{BF}} = 4.2 \times 10^{30} / (\text{m}^3 \text{s})$.

Alternatively, one could follow the work of Walsh *et al.*⁴⁸ and estimate τ as the total simulated time (including the full length of the run for non-successful trajectories and the time for nucleation in the successful ones and dividing by the number of successful runs which is 12 in this case). The final value using this route is $J_{\text{BF}} = 3.4 \times 10^{30} / (\text{m}^3 \text{s})$, which is in excellent agreement with the value obtained using the $\tau_{3/15}$ value.

A different route to determine J is doing a MFPT analysis. The MFPT, $\tau(N)$, is the average elapsed time until the largest cluster of the system reaches or exceeds a threshold size N for

FIG. 4. Number of water molecules in the largest cluster of the CO₂ hydrate, n_h , as a function of time, with supersaturation $S = 1.207$ (a) and 1.268 (b). The cluster size is obtained using the $\bar{q}_3 - \bar{q}_{12}$ linear combination of order parameters. Each curve represents an independent BF NPT simulation at 255 K, 400 bar, and the corresponding saturation. The dashed horizontal line in each panel represents a post-critical cluster that always grows irreversibly and that can be used to determine the nucleation time of each individual run.

the first time. Under reasonably high barriers, $\tau(N)$ is given by the following expression,^{89?}

$$\tau(N) = \frac{\tau_j}{2} \left\{ 1 + \operatorname{erf} \left[Z \sqrt{\pi} (N - N_c) \right] \right\} \quad (14)$$

where $\operatorname{erf}(x)$ is the error function, Z is the Zeldovich factor, N_c critical nucleus size, and $\tau_j = 1/J$ is the inverse of the steady-state nucleation rate J . This expression works well when the growth's time scale is small compared with the time scale for nucleation. Alternatively when they are comparable one could fit the results into the expression:

$$\tau_{mod}(N) = \tau(N) + \frac{1}{2G} (N - N_c) \left\{ 1 + \operatorname{erf} [C(N - N_c)] \right\}, \quad (15)$$

where G is the growth rate and C is a positive constant. In Fig. 5 a MFPT analysis is performed and the results are fitted to both Eqs. (14) (red lines) and (15) (blue lines). The value of J is obtained from the MFPT analysis as:

FIG. 5. MFPT, τ , as a function of the largest cluster size, n_h , obtained for the solution of CO₂ in water at 255 K and 400 bar with supersaturation $S = 1.207$ (a) and 1.268 (b). Note that n_h is given in terms of the number of water molecules in the hydrate phase. Black circles correspond to the average time at which the cluster of water molecules in the hydrate phase reaches for the first time a certain size in the range from 0 to 400 molecules according to the BF simulations plotted in Fig. 4. Continuous curves are fitted using Eqs. (14) (red curve) and (15) (blue curve).

TABLE I. Nucleation rate of CO₂ in water, J , at 255 K, 400 bar, and supersaturation $S = 1.207$ and $S = 1.268$ using the MFPT method.

S	1.207		1.268	
	Eq. (14)	Eq. (15)	Eq. (14)	Eq. (15)
τ_j (ns)	1305.6	1232.4	275.5	197
Z	0.014	0.015	0.007	0.013
$N_c^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	72.2	69.8	86.7	61.7
G (ns ⁻¹)	--	2.64	--	3.03
C	--	0.19	--	179.7
V (nm ³)	172.4	172.4	173.4	173.4
J (m ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	4.4×10^{30}	4.7×10^{30}	2.1×10^{31}	2.9×10^{31}

$$J_{\text{MFPT}} = \frac{1}{\tau_j V} \quad (16)$$

The results for the nucleation rate obtained from the MFPT analysis are shown in Table I.

The summary is that BF simulations lead to values of J of about 4×10^{30} and 2×10^{31} /(m³ s) for $S = 1.207$ and

$S = 1.268$, respectively. For methane hydrate one obtained similar values of J for $S = 4.72$ and 5.67 , respectively. Thus nucleation of CO_2 is easier since it appears at lower supersaturations. What provokes this enhancement of homogeneous nucleation in the CO_2 hydrate? Certainly CO_2 is about one order of magnitude more soluble than CH_4 at the same pressure and supercooling (i.e., $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0803$ for CO_2 versus $x_{\text{CH}_4} = 0.0089$ for methane). However CH_4 seems more efficient. In fact, it is able to reach values of J of the order of 10^{30} with a concentration of $x_{\text{CH}_4} = 0.042$ whereas for CO_2 one needs a concentration of $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.097$ to obtain the same nucleation rate (a similar conclusion was obtained in previous work by some of us on the growth rate of the hydrate⁹⁰). Later in this paper, we will try to identify the key ingredient that makes the homogeneous nucleation of the CO_2 hydrate much easier.

The values of J for $S = 1.207$ of this section will allow to determine if the choice of order parameters to distinguish between hydrate-like and liquid-like water molecules can be used with confidence to correctly determine nucleation rates when using the Seeding technique. Note that J values using this technique are quite sensitive to the choice of the order parameter in contrast with BF runs, which do not depend much on the choice of the order parameter.

C. Nucleation rate from Seeding simulations at $T = 255$ K and supersaturation $S = 1.207$

The Seeding method was implemented as follows. After equilibrating a one-phase system using isotropic NPT simulations at 255 K and 400 bar with $S = 1.207$, we inserted spherical hydrate seeds of different sizes as it is schematized in Fig. 2b. After insertion, we removed particles that overlap with the solid cluster and allowed for a short run where the seed molecules were frozen. After that several NPT runs (with all molecules free to move) with different initial random velocities were performed. When the seed was small the solid cluster quickly melted. When the seed was large the solid cluster grew. Just at the critical size, there is a probability of 50% that the hydrate grows or melts. As can be seen in Fig. 6, when a spherical hydrate seed of radius $r = 0.79$ nm is inserted into the supersaturated solution $S = 1.207$, at 255 K and 400 bar, the system behaves as critical showing 5 trajectories for which the inserted seed grows and 5 in which rapidly melts. The initial size of the seed is calculated by averaging the largest cluster size during the equilibration period of 2 ns in all runs using the selected parameters.

Once we know the critical cluster size, the attachment rate $f_{\text{CO}_2}^+$ can be calculated by averaging the squared difference between the initial cluster size and the cluster size in time. This term behaves linearly and $f_{\text{CO}_2}^+$ is defined as half of the slope of the linear fit according to Eq. (7). Applying this formula to all Seeding runs, we obtain the behavior plotted in Fig. 7 and $f_{\text{CO}_2}^+ = 1.68 \times 10^9 / (\text{s})$. Besides, from our previous work, the driving force at these thermodynamic conditions is $\Delta\mu_{\text{N}} = -2.73 k_B T$. In this way, the Zeldovich factor, Eq. (6) is $Z = 0.123$ and using Eq. (8) we have estimated the

FIG. 6. Number of water molecules in the largest cluster of the CO_2 hydrate, n_h , as a function of time, for the supersaturated solution of CO_2 in water ($S = 1.207$) at 255 K and 400 bar. The starting configuration contains a seed of hydrate of radius $r = 0.79$ nm, which is critical at these conditions. The average size of the cluster, $N_c^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 55$, is obtained using the $\bar{q}_3 - \bar{q}_{12}$ linear combination shown in Fig. 3.

FIG. 7. $\langle [N_c(t) - N_c(t_0)]^2 \rangle$ factor, given in terms of CO_2 molecules, for 10 independent simulations of the supersaturated solution of CO_2 in water ($S = 1.207$) with the critical seed of hydrate at 255 K and 400 bar plotted in Fig. 6. Black circles represent values obtained from simulations and the blue line represents the linear fit of the simulation results.

nucleation rate $J = 1.4 \times 10^{30} / (\text{m}^3 \text{s})$ for a supersaturated solution $S = 1.207$ at 255 K and 400 bar via Seeding approach. As can be noticed, this result is in complete agreement with the findings using BF simulations. According to this, the linear combination of \bar{q}_3 and \bar{q}_{12} can be safely used to describe the correct cluster size. Results of this section are summarized in Table II.

D. Nucleation rate by Seeding simulations at $T = 255$ K and $S = 1$

We were not able to nucleate the hydrate in BF runs at 255 K and 400 bar when having the two-phase system with CO_2 and water at equilibrium (i.e., $S = 1$). Thus we shall use the Seed-

ing method to estimate the nucleation rate after having validated the technique with the results of the previous subsection. The Seeding method was implemented as follows. We first constructed the starting configuration, as shown in Fig. 2c, by equilibrating in the isotropic NPT ensemble a cubic simulation box formed from 12000 water molecules and 1048 CO_2 , i.e., $x_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.0803$ ($S = 1$). Once the temperature, pressure, and average volume achieved a constant value, we add a reservoir of liquid CO_2 at both sides of the previous dissolution forming two planar interfaces with 4952 CO_2 molecules in total, including the reservoir and solution. The z -axis direction is perpendicular to the CO_2 -water interface. Again, this two-phase system is equilibrated in an $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ ensemble keeping constant the cross-section area, \mathcal{A} , with the value being the average area found in the equilibration part before putting the reservoir. We now inserted spherical seeds of CO_2 hydrate of radius between 1.0 and 1.5 nm in the middle of the aqueous phase, removed overlapping particles in the solution, and equilibrated for one or 2 ns. We then performed $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ runs. The length of these runs was about 200 ns. The size of the system (although it fluctuates in the z direction) is about $7.4 \times 7.4 \times 12.4 \text{ nm}^3$.

The size of the largest cluster, as a function of time, is plotted in Fig. 8 for an initial seed of radius $r = 1.01 \text{ nm}$. As can be seen, when the size of the largest cluster is about 115(5) water molecules the cluster becomes critical and thus the seed melts in half of the trajectories and grows in the other half. Notice that this number of water molecules in the hydrate phase corresponds to 19(1) CO_2 molecules also in this phase. The attachment rate can be calculated through the linear fit of $\langle [N_c^{\text{CO}_2}(t) - N_c^{\text{CO}_2}(t_0)]^2 \rangle$, as a function of time, at this condition as is shown in Fig. 9. In this case we estimate $f_{\text{CO}_2}^+ = 6.54 \times 10^8 / (\text{s})$. Using Eq. (2), we find that the free energy barrier of nucleation for the system of CO_2 in water at 255 K, 400 bar, and concentration $S = 1$ is $\Delta G_c = 22(2) k_B T$, which is about 5 times less than that in the case of CH_4 in water at the same supercooling ($\Delta G_c = 95 k_B T$ as we found in our previous work²⁶). The Zeldovich factor is thus $Z = 0.077$ and the nucleation rate estimated using the linear combination of the \bar{q}_3 and \bar{q}_{12} order parameters and Eq. (8) is $J = 2(5) \times 10^{25} / (\text{m}^3 \text{s})$. All results required to estimate the nucleation rate from Seeding are shown in Table II. Our estimate of J at 255 K and 400 bar, for $S = 1$ (i.e., under experimental conditions), namely, $J = 2(5) \times 10^{25} / (\text{m}^3 \text{s})$ is consistent with the value reported at 260 K and 500 bar by Arjun and Bolhuis,⁵⁷ $J = 1 \times 10^{26} / (\text{m}^3 \text{s})$. However, it should be noticed that: (1) the force field used here is similar but not identical to that used by Arjun and Bolhuis (we include here deviations from the Lorentz-Berthelot energetic combining rule for the interaction between the carbon atom of CO_2 and the oxygen of water in contrast to Arjun and Bolhuis); (2) the thermodynamic conditions are slightly different; and (3) Arjun and Bolhuis used a bubble of CO_2 as a reservoir and therefore the solubility of the gas was higher than that of the planar interface implemented in this work. In any case, even taking these differences into account, it seems that the results of this work are consistent with those of Arjun and Bolhuis.⁵⁷

The homogeneous nucleation rate at experimental condi-

FIG. 8. Number of water molecules in the largest cluster of the CO_2 hydrate, n_h , as a function of time, for the saturated solution of CO_2 in water ($S = 1$) at 255 K and 400 bar. The starting configuration contains a seed of hydrate of radius $r = 1.01 \text{ nm}$, which is critical at these conditions. The average size of the cluster, $N_c^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 115$, is obtained using the $\bar{q}_3 - \bar{q}_{12}$ linear combination of the local bond order parameters.

FIG. 9. $\langle [N_c(t) - N_c(t_0)]^2 \rangle$ factor, given in terms of CO_2 molecules, for 10 independent simulations of the saturated solution of CO_2 in water ($S = 1$) with the critical seed of hydrate at 255 K and 400 bar plotted in Fig. 8. Black circles represent values obtained from simulations and the blue line represents the linear fit of the simulation results.

tions for 400 bar and 35 K of supercooling is huge. In fact, it is about 30 orders of magnitude larger than that found for methane under the same conditions (it was found of the order of $10^{-7} / (\text{m}^3 \text{s})$). Therefore, homogeneous nucleation is significantly more important in CO_2 than in CH_4 and will be present in experiments at much higher temperatures. That leads to a very interesting question: what is the factor provoking such a huge difference of J value?

FIG. 10. CO₂ hydrate - solution interfacial free energy, γ , as a function of the inverse critical radius r_c at 255 K and 400 bar. Black circles represent the values found with Seeding for supersaturations $S = 1$ (left) and $S = 1.207$ (right). These values are obtained using the $\bar{q}_3 - \bar{q}_{12}$ linear combination shown in Fig. 3 to get the number of molecules in the cluster. The red line corresponds to a linear fit of the γ values obtained from Seeding. The blue square represents the extrapolated value of γ (22.3 mJ/m²) obtained as $r_c \rightarrow \infty$ (planar interface).

TABLE II. Nucleation rate of CO₂ in water, J , at 255 K, 400 bar, and supersaturations $S = 1$ and 1.207 using the Seeding methodology.

S	1.0	1.207
$N_c^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	115	55
$N_c^{\text{CO}_2}$	20	9.6
Z	0.077	0.123
ΔG_c (ns ⁻¹)	22.6	13.06
$f_{\text{CO}_2}^+$	6.54×10^8	1.68×10^9
J (m ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	2×10^{25}	1.36×10^{30}
γ (mJ/m ²)	18.66	17.63

E. Interfacial free energy between the hydrate and the aqueous solution

It is interesting to analyze in detail the expression leading to J when using CNT (which is the expression used in the Seeding technique), and particularly Eqs. (5) and (8) in the context of the CO₂ and CH₄ hydrates. According to Eq. (5), J is given by the product of a kinetic prefactor, J_0 , and a free energy barrier within an exponential term. The comparison of J_0 for CH₄ and CO₂ hydrates shows that they are quite similar. They only differ in one order of magnitude but we must explain 30 orders of magnitude of difference. The Zeldovich factor of the CO₂ hydrate is twice that of methane, but the attachment rate is one-half so that the product of Z and f^+ are almost identical in both cases. The density of the gas in the liquid phase is about one order of magnitude larger for CO₂ than for CH₄ (due to its higher solubility in water). Thus the higher solubility of CO₂ in water only affects one order of magnitude the prefactor J_0 of the expression of J . Therefore, differences must come from the exponential free energy barrier, which has two components, $\Delta\mu_N$ and N_c . For $S = 1$, $\Delta\mu_N$

amounts to -2.26 and $-2.42k_B T$ for the CO₂ and CH₄ hydrates, respectively. This goes in the right direction, as for a certain fixed value of N_c the free energy barrier will be smaller for CO₂ than for CH₄. However, the difference does not seem so large to explain the difference in the nucleation rate. The difference in the nucleation rate comes from N_c which contains 83 molecules of methane but only 20 of CO₂ at the same conditions. This is the key to understanding the differences: the critical cluster of the CO₂ hydrate is much smaller than that of the CH₄ hydrate. To analyze the physical origin of the difference let us consider Eq. (3) which describes the critical cluster size. Values of ρ_s and $\Delta\mu_N$ are quite similar for both hydrates. Therefore the key for the different behaviors must be on the value of the interfacial free energy γ that moreover appears elevated to the third power.

Using Eq. (3) one can calculate the values of γ as a function of the critical cluster radius for systems with $S = 1$ and $S = 1.207$ at $T = 255$ K and 400 bar and with these values extrapolate γ to the planar interface ($r_c \rightarrow \infty$) as shown in Fig. 10. For $S = 1$ the value of γ for the CO₂ system is around 19 mJ/m² and the extrapolation to the hydrate-water planar interface yields 22.3 mJ/m². Notice that this value of the planar interface is not at the three-phase coexistence point but at the two-phase (hydrate-liquid) equilibrium at 250 K and 400 bar for the planar interface. See Fig. 13 of our last work on nucleation.²⁶ However, for the CH₄ hydrate the value of γ is of about 32 mJ/m² when $S = 1$ and of about 39 mJ/m² for the planar hydrate-water interface. Thus the higher nucleation rate of J for the CO₂ hydrate as compared to the CH₄ hydrate arises from a lower value of γ that decreases significantly the free energy barrier. Although it is almost impossible to present a molecular explanation one could argue that when the composition of the fluid phase is more similar to that of the hydrate (which has a molar fraction of the gas molecule of $8/54 = 0.148$) the interfacial free energy becomes smaller. The higher values of γ for the CH₄ hydrate-water interface would arise from a larger difference in composition between the aqueous phase and the hydrate. Thus the higher solubility of CO₂ in water would affect the nucleation rate not in the kinetic prefactor, which only contributes to the different in one order of magnitude, nor in the value of $\Delta\mu_N$ but on decreasing significantly the value of γ .

There is an additional interesting observation. The value of γ of the hydrate-water planar interface for the CO₂ systems seems to increase with temperature along the two-phase coexistence line. In fact, for 255 K the estimated value is 22 mJ/m² whereas γ is around 30(2) mJ/m² at $T_3 = 290$ K at this pressure according to previous calculations by some of us using the mold integration host and guest methodology.^{82,83}

F. Nucleation along the $S = 1$ curve

The value of J at 255 K for $S = 1$ is of the order of $10^{25}/(\text{m}^3\text{s})$. Nucleation can be observed spontaneously in BF runs when the nucleation rate is larger than $10^{29}/(\text{m}^3\text{s})$ with current computational resources. Therefore, it seems likely that nucleation can be observed in BF runs at $S = 1$ if we move

to lower temperatures (thus increasing the driving force). This is of particular interest as nucleation studies in experiments are usually performed along the $S = 1$ curve (with the solution in contact with a gas reservoir⁹¹).

We performed BF runs at 245 and 250 K (and 400 bar) at the corresponding CO₂ saturation concentration. These states are represented as red diamonds in Fig. 1 (note that they are located on the $S = 1$ red line). Details on these simulations are given in Table III. As we have already mentioned, we used two types of simulation setups for this study: a homogeneous CO₂ saturated bulk solution (denoted as “one-phase system” in Table III) and a saturated solution in contact with a fluid CO₂ reservoir (denoted as “two-phase system” in Table III). We focus first on the one-phase system and analyze later on the comparison between both setups. We used isotropic NPT runs for the one-phase systems. As not all trajectories were successful in nucleating the solid phase, we used the method of Walsh et al.⁴⁸, described previously in the manuscript when discussing the BF runs for $S = 1.207$, to determine the nucleation rate. We obtain a nucleation rate of the order of $10^{31}/(\text{m}^3\text{s})$ for 245 K and of $10^{29}/(\text{m}^3\text{s})$ for 250 K. These nucleation rates are fully consistent with the $J = 10^{25} \text{m}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$ obtained in this work for $S = 1$ at 255 K via Seeding (see Section III D). The J values obtained from BF simulations along the $S = 1$ line (red circles) are compared with that obtained via Seeding for $S = 1$ (green triangle) in Fig. 11a.

In the following sections, we describe how we combine our nucleation studies at $S = 1$ and three different temperatures (245, 250, and 255 K) with a recent calculation of γ between the solid and the solution at the three-phase coexistence temperature⁸² to get an estimate of the whole $J(T)$ curve along the $S = 1$ line.

1. γ along $S = 1$

To estimate J along $S = 1$ we need first to know how γ varies along $S = 1$, given that the nucleation barrier can be obtained from γ through Eq. (4). We already have a value of γ from Seeding at $S = 1$ and 255 K (18.7mJ/m^2 , depicted with a green triangle in Fig. 11b). Recently, some of us estimated γ at the T_3 (the temperature where solid, solution and CO₂ reservoir coexists,⁸² indicated by a maroon circle in Fig. 1 for $S = 1$). The value found was $29(2) \text{mJ/m}^2$ at 287 K. The T_3 value was later refined to 290 K.⁷⁰ We assume here that the value of γ found in the work of Algaba and collaborators⁸² at 287 K is valid for the updated T_3 of 290 K (the temperature difference between both T_3 estimates is small). The value of γ at T_3 is shown as a blue square in Fig. 11b).

We now try to get an estimate of γ from the two BF simulation studies performed at 245 and 250 K. To do that we use Eq. (5) to get ΔG_c from J and, then, Eq. (4) to obtain γ from ΔG_c (the CO₂ density in the solid phase used for these calculations is $\rho_s^{\text{CO}_2} = 4.7 \times 10^{27} \text{m}^{-3}$ for both temperatures). The first of these two steps requires an estimate of J_0 . To estimate J_0 we need f^+ . We use the fact that f^+ is proportional to the CO₂ diffusion coefficient, D_{CO_2} , and to $N_c^{2/3}$,²² to obtain f^+ at 245 and 250 K from the f^+ calculated at 255 K.

TABLE III. Simulation details and results obtained using BF simulations at 250 and 245 K, both at 400 bar and supersaturation $S = 1$ in one- and two-phase systems.

	one-phase system	two-phase system
T (K)	250	
$N^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	6524	7200
N^{CO_2}	606	3444
x_{CO_2}	0.085	0.085
box dim. (nm ³)	$6.06 \times 6.06 \times 6.06$	$9.07 \times 6.25 \times 7.41$
liquid dim. (nm ³)	$6.06 \times 6.06 \times 6.06$	$5.77 \times 6.25 \times 7.41$
V_{liq} (nm ³)	222	267
n_{runs}	12	12
n_{nucl}	4	4
t_{nucl} (ns)	730	245
	1310	285
	1570	480
	1700	1510
t_{total} (ns)	21310	18520
$\rho_L^{\text{CO}_2}$ (m ⁻³)	2.7×10^{27}	2.7×10^{27}
J (m ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	8.45×10^{29}	8.09×10^{29}
T (K)	245	
$N^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	2400	2400
N^{CO_2}	240	1148
x_{CO_2}	0.09	0.09
box dim. (nm ³)	$4.35 \times 4.35 \times 4.35$	$9.19 \times 6.25 \times 2.47$
V_{liq} (nm ³)	82.5	82.5
n_{runs}	2	2
n_{nucl}	2	2
t_{nucl} (ns)	640	300
	550	230
t_{total} (ns)	1190	530
$\rho_L^{\text{CO}_2}$ (m ⁻³)	2.9×10^{27}	2.9×10^{27}
J (m ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	2.02×10^{31}	5.78×10^{31}

This requires computing D_{CO_2} at 245, 250, and 255 K and estimating N_c in the BF runs. The CO₂ diffusion coefficients we get from NPT simulations of the aqueous solutions are 1.6, 2.2, and $3.0 \times 10^{-11} \text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ for 245, 250, and 255 K respectively. To estimate N_c we identify the largest cluster that appears during the induction period previous to hydrate growth (see Fig. 12). In this way, we get 42 and 95 water molecules in the critical cluster at 245 and 250 K, respectively, which are values fully consistent with $N_c^{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 115$ obtained with Seeding at 255 K. While this estimate of N_c might not be accurate, the final value of γ is not significantly influenced by this inaccuracy, as we argue further on. The $|\Delta\mu_N|$ factor in J_0 is taken from our previous work using the route 4.⁷⁰ We get $|\Delta\mu_N| = 2.98$ and $2.59 k_B T$ at 245 and 250 K, respectively. With these ingredients we obtain the γ estimates shown in Fig. 11b as red circles (14.6 and 16.0mJ/m^2 at 245 and 250 K respectively).

The γ estimates from BF simulations (red circles), from Seeding simulations (green triangles), and from Mold Integration (blue square) are fully consistent among each other and can be fitted quite nicely to a straight line (maroon line). γ increases with temperature along the $S = 1$ line roughly at a rate of 1mJ/m^2 every 3 K.

Interestingly, BF simulations yield a γ value less sensitive to the order parameter than the Seeding method. In Seeding,

FIG. 11. CO₂ hydrate nucleation rate, J , (a) and CO₂ hydrate-water interfacial free energy, γ , (b), as functions of temperature along the $S = 1$ curve. Red circles and green triangles are BF and Seeding results obtained in this work, respectively. The blue square is the CO₂ hydrate-water interfacial free energy at coexistence conditions obtained by Algaba *et al.*⁸² through the Mold Integration.⁹² Continuous curve in (a) is obtained using simulation data via the CNT approach and line in (b) is a linear fit of simulation data. The curve of J as a function of time is obtained using the $\gamma(T)$ dependence found in (b). The dashed horizontal line in (a) corresponds to an “unachievable” nucleation rate given by one nucleus per universe age and hydro-sphere volume.

Eq. (3) is used to infer γ from the N_c value obtained in seeded simulations, which has a strong dependence on the chosen order parameter. In contrast, in the BF approach, N_c is used for estimating the kinetic pre-factor. As the natural logarithm of this pre-factor is taken to calculate ΔG_c (from which γ is then obtained via Eq. (4)), the influence of N_c on the final γ value is relatively minor. To illustrate this, let us consider the impact of doubling the cluster size in the calculation of γ . In Seeding (255 K), γ would significantly increase from 18.7 to 23.5 mJ/m². However, in BF simulations, the changes are much smaller: from 14.6 to 14.9 mJ/m² at 245 K, and from 16.0 to 16.2 mJ/m² at 250 K. In conclusion: (i) BF simulations provide an estimate of γ less influenced by the choice of order parameter than Seeding; (ii) the way in which we obtain N_c from BF simulations is good enough to get a reliable estimate of γ .

FIG. 12. Number of water molecules in the largest cluster of the CO₂ hydrate, n_h , as a function of time, for different bulk simulations at $S = 1$ and 250 K. CO₂ hydrate growth is observed in four trajectories. The dashed horizontal line, which highlights the largest sub-critical cluster that emerged in all simulations, is our estimate for $N_c^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ using the $\bar{q}_3 - \bar{q}_{12}$ linear combination of the local bond order parameters (95 in the present example).

2. J along $S = 1$

Using the linear fit of $\gamma(T)$ shown in Fig. 11b, we can obtain ΔG_c at any temperature using Eq. (5) with the $|\Delta\mu_N|$ obtained in our previous work (route 4).⁷⁰ We use the following fit for the chemical potential difference: $|\Delta\mu_N|/(k_B T) = -3.02 \times 10^{-4} T^2 + 0.228 T - 40.7$. With ΔG_c and Eq. (8) we can estimate J at any temperature provided that we have J_0 as well. This requires having f^+ at any T (see Eq. (5)). For that purpose, we use again the fact that $f^+ \propto N_c^{2/3} D_{\text{CO}_2}$.²² On the one hand, through NPT simulations of the saturated aqueous solution at different temperatures, we got the following fit to obtain D_{CO_2} at any temperature: $\ln[D/(\text{m}^2/\text{s})] = -0.0011 T^2 + 0.6846 T - 124.99$. On the other hand, N_c can be obtained at any T using $\Delta G_c = N_c |\Delta\mu|/2$ according to Eq. (2). The missing factors to complete the calculation of J_0 (and of J) are the Zeldovich factor Z , that can be easily computed through N_c and $|\Delta\mu_N|$ (Eq. (6)), and $\rho_L^{\text{CO}_2}$ which is trivially obtained in NPT simulations. With these ingredients, we can draw the maroon curve in Fig. 11a that predicts the trend of the nucleation rate at $S = 1$.

Unfortunately, to the best of our knowledge, there is no experimental data to compare these simulation predictions with. In homogeneous ice nucleation, rates of the order of 10^2 to $10^{30} \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ are experimentally accessible.⁹³ Our predictions indicate that such rates occur at temperatures below 266 K (beyond 25 K supercooling). Therefore, we hope that simulations and experiments of homogeneous hydrate nucleation can be compared in the future, as they were for the case of ice nucleation.⁹³

3. Bulk versus surface nucleation

The dashed horizontal line in Fig. 11a indicates the order of magnitude of an unachievable nucleation rate: that corresponding to 1 nucleus formed in the volume of the hydrosphere and in the age of the universe. Our CNT fit (maroon curve) predicts that this unattainable rate occurs at about 272 K (around 20 K below T_3). Therefore, any crystallization event at a supercooling lower than 20 K must be heterogeneous (the difficulty of observing homogeneous nucleation was also highlighted in a simulation study of methane hydrates).¹⁹ In most experiments, hydrate crystallization typically for supercooling smaller than 20 K supercooling.^{40,94,95} Such low supercooling suggests that the nucleation of hydrates is not homogeneous in the real world. Although experiments do not provide molecular insight into the nucleation step, it is commonly believed that nucleation occurs at the gas-solution interface, perhaps assisted by impurities, the glass-solution contact line,⁹⁶ or aided by an increased concentration of the hydrate formed near the interface.⁹⁷

To investigate the latter hypothesis we compare BF simulation runs at 245 and 250 K performed in two-phase systems (where the solution is in contact with a CO₂ reservoir) with those run in one-phase systems that have been already presented (without a bulk aqueous solution having the equilibrium CO₂ saturation concentration). In the two-phase simulations, the details of which are reported in Table III, we used $NP_2 \mathcal{A} T$ runs. Obviously, the volume used to calculate the nucleation rate is only that of the aqueous phase in two-phase systems. As reported in Table III, both simulation setups give the same nucleation rate for both temperatures (within less than half an order of magnitude). Therefore, the CO₂-solution interface does not have any effect on hydrate nucleation, at least at 245 and 250 K. However, there could be a crossover between homogeneous and heterogeneous nucleation as the temperature increases (as is the case for crystallization of hard spheres with density)⁹⁸ that could explain nucleation events at low supercooling. More research is needed to identify the nucleation path in mild supercooling conditions, where hydrate formation is experimentally observed.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have calculated the homogeneous nucleation rate of CO₂ hydrate at 400 bar and 255 K (35 K of supercooling) using Classical Nucleation Theory and Seeding simulations. For supersaturated systems (i.e., $S = 1.207$ and $S = 1.268$) the nucleation rate can be obtained from BF simulations. Since the results of Seeding depend on the choice of the order parameter we tested that a combination of \bar{q}_3 and \bar{q}_{12} is able to distinguish in an efficient way molecules of water belonging to the liquid or to the hydrate with a mislabeling of about 0.02%. By using this combination of order parameters in Seeding runs with $S = 1.207$ we confirmed that it provides an estimate of J in full agreement with that obtained from BF runs. In other words, the selected order parameter allows a satisfactory estimate of the radius of the solid critical cluster

at the surface of tension.

After checking the adequacy of the order parameter we implemented the Seeding technique (in a system having two phases) for $S = 1$ at 255 K and 400 bar. We obtained a size of 115 molecules of water for the critical cluster and a value of $10^{25}/(\text{m}^3\text{s})$ for the nucleation rate. This is about 30 orders of magnitude larger than the value obtained in our previous work for the methane hydrate at the same pressure and supercooling. The higher solubility of CO₂ is not sufficient to explain such an enormous difference. We identify that the key is a much lower value of γ for the CO₂ hydrate-water interface when compared to that of the CH₄ hydrate-water interface, and speculate that the value of γ in these systems could be lower when the composition of the solution becomes closer to the composition of the hydrate. The interfacial free energy of the CO₂ hydrate at $S = 1$ was of about 19 mJ/m² as compared to the value of 29 mJ/m² obtained in our previous work for the methane hydrate. This means that at the same supercooling, the nucleation rate of CO₂ hydrate is 30 orders of magnitude higher than the estimation found in our last work of nucleation rate of methane hydrate²⁶ and 20 orders of magnitude higher than the nucleation rate of ice I_h which at this pressure and supercooling is of around $J_h = 10^5/(\text{m}^3\text{s})$.⁹⁹

Finally, we found that the energy to create the hydrate-liquid interface is $\gamma = 22.3 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ at 255 K and 400 bar, this suggests that the interfacial free energy for a planar interface should increase as the system moves along the two-phase curve from this supercooling temperature to the T_3 , where γ is around 30(2) mJ/m² according to experiments^{100–103} and our previous calculations using the mold integration host and guest methodology.^{82,83}

Finally, we have shown that BF runs in a two-phase system can indeed be performed to nucleate the hydrate at 245 and 250 K to obtain J when $S = 1$ at these temperatures. Comparison of the value of J from simulations using two phases with a system having just one phase reveals that the water-CO₂ interface does not enhance the nucleation rate so that at least for temperatures below 255 K the nucleation is homogeneous and there is not an enhancement of the nucleation rate due to heterogeneous nucleation at the water-CO₂ interface. However, most likely there could be a crossover to heterogeneous nucleation at higher temperatures so that it is the main path to nucleation when closer to the equilibrium temperature T_3 . Finally, we estimate the value of J along the $S = 1$ curve concluding that homogeneous nucleation could indeed be determined experimentally at this pressure for supercooling larger than 25 K. Our simulations predict that homogeneous nucleation is not viable for supercooling lower than 20 K. Therefore, nucleation must be heterogeneous in typical experiments where hydrate formation is observed at low supercooling.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was financed by Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (Grant No. PID2021-125081NB-I00), Junta de Andalucía (P20-00363), and Universidad de Huelva (P.O. FEDER UHU-1255522, FEDER-UHU-202034, and

EPIT1282023), all five cofinanced by EU FEDER funds. We greatly acknowledge the RES resources provided by the Barcelona Supercomputing Center in Mare Nostrum to FI-2023-2-0041. The authors also acknowledge Project No. PID2019-105898GB-C21 of the Ministerio de Educación y Cultura. We also acknowledge access to supercomputer time from RES from project FI-2022-1-0019. J. G. gratefully acknowledges Polish high-performance computing infrastructure PLGrid (HPC Center: ACK Cyfronet AGH) for providing computer facilities and support within computational grant no. PLG/2024/017195. Part of the computations were carried out at the Centre of Informatics Tricity Academic Supercomputer & Network. C. Vega, E. Sanz, and S. Blázquez acknowledge the funding from project PID2022-136919NB-C31 of Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Iván M. Zerón: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (lead); Formal analysis (lead); Investigation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Jesús Algaba:** Conceptualization (lead); Data curation (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **José Manuel Míguez:** Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Joanna Grabowska:** Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Samuel Blázquez:** Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Eduardo Sanz:** Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Carlos Vega:** Conceptualization (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Felipe J. Blas:** Conceptualization (lead); Investigation (lead); Methodology (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available within the article.

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